

TITLE

Search for Home and the Echoes of partition: Tracing the Language of Incommunicable trauma of an Internal ‘Outsider’ in the Bengali Novel of Pataur Jaman, *Amake khun korle kano*.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The entire oeuvre of Indian diasporic studies is not limited to and within the discussion of transnational migrants but it comes into focus on the narrative of the internal migration too, a variety of ethno-regional diaspora, where the migrants, here Bengalis, being driven by the pull factors of better opportunity and security in host states, are found to leave their home-states by choice and reside in various states of Indian territory. Unlike a transnational migrant who is treated as a political minority in a host land due to his national identity, an internal migrant becomes a linguistic and cultural minority in the host state. But an internal migrant like a transnational migrant experiences the same marginality, the aporia of home in imagination and his subordination to the alien cultural hegemony makes him the ethno-regional ‘other’ and compel the displaced subject, in a diasporic sense, to search for his indigenous roots. The inability of an internal migrant to come back to his own home-state or during the COVID-19 pandemic the treatment of a poor internal migrant as the spreader of virus, as outsiders and his social exclusion, ostracisation and a state of imprisonment in inferior, poor-quality spaces often culminate in a diasporic resolution or death that mirrors the harsh reality of a victim of partition also where the issues of settlement, poor quality ghettos, colonies, forced mobilisation underscore the spatial exclusion of a subject in both the cases, reiterating the truth that a migrant is a nobody or a body that belongs to no state ultimately. The paper takes an informed look at the fragmented existence, discontinuous voices and nomadic identities of the Bengali migrants in the perspective of a Bengali novel *why did you kill me* (*Amake khun korle kano*) by Pataur Jaman.

RESEARCH GAP

There has been very little discussion of how the marginalised Bengali migrants are residing under the complex social matrix of various states of India and how the exilic identity of Bengali diasporic community is being shaped and reshaped by the dominant social culture of the states in the context of regional diasporic discourse.

METHODOLOGY

It would involve a qualitative analysis through the close reading of the text with the help of post-modernism and other socio-cultural theories.

WHAT IS NEW ABOUT THE PAPER

It would highlight the trauma of the displaced Bengali migrants, both skilled and unskilled, within the domestic territory of India in the present scenario and would portray how the socio-political forces, from the times of past to that of pandemic, working behind the plights of the expatriates culminated in the creation of cultural displacement that make them psychological refugees.

KEYWORDS

Regional Diaspora/Domestic migration, Exile, Alienation, Identity, Nostalgia, Minority, Marginalisation, Migration Trauma

Pataur Jaman with the publication of his Bengali debut novel *Amake khun korle kano* (*Why did you kill me*) in 2022, unfailingly catches the trauma and dilemma of an internal migrant worker, Bulbul. Based on the theme of domestic migration and pandemic precarity, this is presumably the first Bengali realistic fiction where the narrative is unmistakably tinged with diaspora consciousness. This is a Bengali realistic fiction written in first-person narrative. It is a story about Bulbul, an internal migrant worker who is from minority community. He returns home in pandemic situation. On his arrival he is refused to stay with his family members by local leader Hazi chacha and his people. With other migrant workers (Santu, Mintu, Khoka and Bhola) he is forced to stay quarantined in a school for fourteen days. During the period of his isolation he discovers Santu as a sycophant of Hazi chacha. Bulbul comes to know that Santu has murdered brother Majed, a supposed enemy of Hazi by bombing and he understands in due course that Hazi is a corrupted person and he charges illegal commission from all the government grants released for local area projects. When Bulbul threatens Santu to expose all the secrets of which Santu is a part, Santu with the help of others planned to murder him. On the thirteenth night, they mix up some sleep inducing sedatives with his meat broth secretly and when Bulbul sleeps at night after having his dinner, they strangle him to death and brutally kill him. They put the dead body in a plastic sack and bury it without performing any rights at the root of a palm tree. In the fictionalized version of narrative the readers observe that his brain continues functioning for more than ten minutes after the body has died. The speaker is thus a dead migrant worker who tells the whole story of his life by jumping into his past life and then coming back to his present situation. Before proceeding in the direction of how the writing has provided an inside view of the problems endured by internal migrants of India, the words diaspora, migration, domestic or internal

migration, trauma, nostalgia, memory, identity formation, exile, alienation, hybridism, pandemic precarity require a clear information.

Derived from the Greek, the word ‘diaspora’ literally means “scattering or dispersion” and is applied to the forced or voluntary movement of a large and culturally similar group of people from their place of origin or homeland to a completely new and different part of the world. Though as a phenomenon it existed since the arrival of human civilization on earth but as a term, it referred to the displacement of Jewish community into another geographic and cultural region. Though the term ‘diaspora’ was used to refer to displaced populations, it is now increasingly used to refer to migrants who being the part of a particular community feels connected to its ‘prior home’.(Clifford 1994) Migration is the trans-border movement of people with the intension of settling permanently or temporarily. This type of movement could be from one country to another or in the form of internal migration. The terms ‘in migration’ and ‘out migration’ are used for migration within a country. Bhagat, in an article named “ Assessing the Measurement of Internal Migration in India”, talks about different types of internal or domestic migration and says that “ It is possible to identify three types of internal migration – intra-district, inter-district and inter-state and to determine four streams of internal migration per type, namely, rural to urban, urban to rural, rural to rural, and urban to urban” (Bhagat 93) Trauma is a psychological condition indicating a particular experience arising out of a very stressful situation . Nostalgia is a feeling of pleasure mixed with sadness when a person thinks about some events of past. Memory is the psychological process of gathering, saving, holding onto, and later recovering information. It is composed of three processes: encoding, storage and retrieval. Identity formation refers to a perception of identity that is formed by the ambience surrounding one. It is based on the cultural and religious beliefs, class and social status to which an individual belongs. The word exile refers to a particular situation in which somebody is forced to leave the homeland or his/her ‘point of origin’ and stay outside the place of nativity. Alienation refers to the state of isolation from one’s own environment, other people or self. Hybridism refers to the combination or negotiation of two or more things together. Precarity is a situation in which a person experiences financial insecurity and mental breakdown due to the lack of regular income. Pandemic precarity refers to the adverse social experience of a person, here migrant worker, in pandemic situations. Migration trauma is a kind of psychological agony of a subject who being compelled to leave his/her home state or being denied to enter the birthplace experiences a deep emotional suffering and fear concerning the migration process.

People leave their homeland for various reasons. Earlier, in the precolonial time the first wave of diasporians included uneducated people who were forcibly taken to other countries (British colonies like Figi, Trinidad and Mauritius) to do the labour work under a master but in postcolonial phase the second wave included the literate, qualified professionals who willingly move to the foreign land to get a better tomorrow. A migrant worker is fully aware of the fact that the host land is full of problems but the opportunities it gives are missing in his/her homeland. Under the complex social matrix of India, an internal migrant almost like an international one leave the homeland and shares some common experiences like problem of identity, alienation, nostalgia, dislocation, loss of cultural values that the present paper is

purported to showcase in Pataur Jaman's Bengali realistic fiction *Amake khun korle kano* (*Why did you kill me*). The census of 2011 indicates that almost forty six percent of Indian urban population is comprised of migrants as they occupy a significant amount of space in large urban centres. They work in construction and manufacturing, textiles and brick making and almost in all formal and informal sectors (Srivastava and Sutradhar 2016; Deshingkar and Akter 2009). With the same intention Bulbul, the central migrant character leaves his home but the exilic experiences he encountered during his travel explore unfathomable pangs of marginalised minorities, especially those of migrant workers. Since the entire oeuvre of migration literature is preoccupied with the experiences of dislocation, the exilic trauma casts an indelible impact on the language of displaced subject. There is, as if, an attempt on the part of the speaker to negotiate between the two polarities. Most of the writings of migration literature take two moves. The analepsis focuses his past lives and the prolepsis indicates his movement to the future. Each time the story starts with the present scenario and then it moves in flashbacks. Bulbul has gone to various states and districts of India not to settle permanently over there but for earning money. He has moved for better future and possibilities. He dreams that he will come back and open a grocery shop in his village with the money. His temporary encounter with the foreign cultures of the states could not conform him into acculturation but rather whenever he found himself alienated in a new society and new culture, he escaped from the harsh reality and took refuge in his school days and the days of his childhood down his memory lane. He could recollect the days when his mother used to tell him stories from religious texts and he identified himself with the characters of most of the stories. Thus he used to bear his unique ethno-religious identity even in the host land. He refuses to be homogenised. He was questioned, he was challenged, he was ridiculed time and again but his cultural identity was no less a source of pride, peace and strength for him and he refused to part with it. The very first chapter starts with his name "Din Ak: Naam Holo Amar Bulbul (Dau One: My Name is Bulbul) where he introduces the name of his father and his family lineage. "My father ('abba') was Khorsed Alam. He got his name from my grandfather Aakbbar Ali. I was named Bulbul Uddin. Everybody in my school told me that I am a bird. When asked Samir told, 'see, the name of my father is Asim Chatterjee and my name is Samir Chatterjee. But your name is Bulbul Uddin and your father is Khorsed Alam. So how can you be your father's son! If you were your father's son your name would have been Bulbul Alam. Is not it? That is why you are a bird...And you know what everybody says if you are not your father's son!' Telling this Samir used to laugh at me." (Jaman 8) The primary identity of Bulbul is that he is a Muslim from lower middle class and Samir is a Hindu and Bulbul represents the treatment that minority community gets from the majority people of his time. The religio-centric politics shaped and reshaped by the majoritarian consensus of Hindutwa of modern India relegates the minorities to the 'ghetto'. They are treated as 'other' in their own homeland, India. They are ridiculed and questioned for their seemingly different name cultures. Even they are denied their human existence. Bulbul's existence was reduced to the level of a non-human species. They have no world or they are alien in their own world since Muslim bodies, representing heterogeneous societal culture, are conceived of as 'other' in modern India. Everywhere he was questioned for his name and for his use of language and his error of misusing his language was, as if, subjected to correction by 'them'. This disjunction between two cultures often resulted in dislocation for Bulbul. Muslims in Bengal

often use the word ‘pani’ instead of ‘jol’ for water. But when he stood up and asked for permission from his Arjun sir to go outside the classroom for having a glass of ‘pani’, the whole class laughed at his use of the word ‘pani’ and Arjun sir told by addressing him a donkey, “ It is not pani, it would be jol”.(Jaman 83) Thus he describes his dilemma not only in the chapter “ Din Choy: Neem Gacher Chand” (Day Six: The Moon of Margosa Tree) but also in another chapter entitled “Fera”(Return) where he says, “If I would answered somebody by saying that my father’s name is Khorsed Alam, everyone laughed at me. From then on, I never introduced my father as ‘abba’ but as ‘baba’”(a term majorly used by Hindus of Bengal to denote father).(Jaman 148) This acculturation is the outcome of his adoption, acquisition and adjustment to a different cultural environment. That they are marginalised in their own country is evinced by another significant move by the Indian government which by enacting the Citizenship Amendment Act on 12 December 2019 and by passing an amendment thereafter in 2019 (CAA 2019) announced that the process of registration of citizens will be completed soon. This was widely criticised for being grounded on racial discrimination and the nation observed a series of protests as it might be used to deprive Muslims. Bulbul in the chapter entitled “ Din-Char: Goru Gulo Ato Hamba Hamba Kore Daake Kano? (Day-Four: Why Do The Cows Moo ?) says, “I must hear the news. Otherwise how shall I be informed of my country? Without this, when we are really in a problem concerning the registration of citizens we must hear the news.” (Jaman 56) The politics of religious exclusivism exercised by the Hindu majority of his country turned him a politico-national ‘other’ in his own country and the disjunctured self like Bulbul is compelled to search for their space and their identity. The narrative is fraught not only with the marginalisation on religious level but also on the level of socio-cultural aspects as Bulbul has another identity as a migrant worker. He represents a poverty-ridden lower middle class where there is no earning member. In the chapter named “Ami Akjon Porijayi Shromik”(I am a Migrant Worker) Bulbul says that his father used to earn as an agricultural labourer and as a contract worker and find it difficult to make both ends meet. So, to earn money, Bulbul decided to go to Delhi and he goes against the decision of his parents. His mother tried to convince him to finish study by saying, “Don’t worry about money. It will be managed.” But Bulbul replied, “ The factor is not all about money. What shall I do by receiving education? Who will give me job? Job is impossible without bribes! We are not that rich!”(Jaman 17) Thus, like many others, domestic or internal migration of Bulbul was comprised of both intra-state (from district to district covering short distance) and inter-state(from state to state covering a long distance within India) migrations for better opportunities. In India, “the push and pull factors have dominated much of the understanding of migration. Push factors like low income, low literacy, dependence on agriculture and high poverty are cited as some examples associated with place of origin. On the other hand, high income, high literacy, dominance of industries and services are the pull factors associated with the place of destination.”(Bhagat 17) But wherever he went as a worker, be it within the state of West Bengal or outside, he faced the same question of his identity and was answered that he was not from there but from outside and he is an outsider. In the chapter entitled “ Ami Ekhanar Noi” (I am Not from Here) Bulbul said, “ Later I came to know that we are the migrant workers...the time when I was in Purulia for the purpose of road construction, I learnt practically the meaning of a migrant worker.” His identity was compared with that of a

migratory bird. He flies out to different parts of the country where the conditions are better but returns home after a certain period of time when his job is over just like a migratory bird does. Someone says, the migratory birds “Have no fixed country (home) to return. I protested saying, ‘I have a country, I have a village, I have a police station.’ He says that I have everything, but is it mine! That country belongs to the local leaders, to the police officers, to the BDOs! Where am I there?”(Jaman 22) This nomadic identity is characteristic with all migrant workers like Bulbul. When he comes home he was isolated (quarantined) for fourteen days unlike the son of Hazi chacha as they are not the same. His movement was restricted and he was separated from his family members with the false suspicion that he was exposed to a contagious disease. He was jailed within the four walls of a school where his behaviour was monitored. In the name of government rules, he was observed whether he was normal or sick. When his manners were proved ill and he spoke ill of them, they decided to kill him just like a virus. Thus the catastrophe of a downtrodden Bengali migrant minority worker like Bulbul results in double marginalisation. It is not only the political leader of the locality but the governments of the nation also that show indifference to them. The experiences of migrant informal workers during the pandemic situation were appalling as the time was marked not only with the termination, abandonment, despair and hyper- precarity of the workers but also spotted with the plight of return migration of the workers as the government lacks a proper and effective planning needed for it. In the chapter named “Din – Panch: Amar Dayitwo Nebe Ke” (Day –Five:Who will Take My Responsibility) Bulbul says, ‘ I noticed some news started flashing automatically in the Google news. ‘Passenger train is running, though state has revoked its responsibility regarding this. They are not going to spend money for it.

At least fifteen migrants died by mowing down on the railway tracks in the district of Aurangabad of Maharashtra. Report of the Railway Board says, those workers after being locked down for long days were coming back home walking along the tracks. But ultimately, the workers of Madhya Pradesh failed to return home.’ (Jaman 70) “On 24th March 2020, in order to contain the virus, a strict nationwide lockdown was imposed by India with immediate sealing of the inter-state and international borders within four hours of its announcement. This shocked the unprepared migrant workers, both internal and those working abroad... The lack of governmental planning to ensure the well-being of migrant workers within India and abroad led to a “crisis within a crisis”.”(Khan and Arokkiaraj.2) In the chapter entitled “Din –Panch: Amar Dayitwo Nebe Ke”(Day- Five:Who will Take My Responsibility) Bulbul introduces the readers with one of his co-workers, Arup who sent a voice message saying, ‘Locked down for ten days. No work to do. As a result no money in my hand. And I cannot buy food due to the lack of money. The hotel at which I used to go to eat meals was closed by administration. Yesterday a local leader came and told us to return home.’(Jaman 69) The situation of the migrant workers in pandemic situation was worse. “Due to the COVID-19-induced lockdown, the working class, especially the low-income migrant workers, have been the worst affected (Pandey, 2020). They were retrenched in large numbers, were rendered unemployed with their wages unpaid in the destination states which forced them to return to their origin states. Lokesh, one of our respondents and a construction worker who returned from Karnataka to Odisha, the lack of employment and

wage theft pushed him to return to his native state during the lockdown. Similarly, Mahesh who was working in a hotel when the lockdown was imposed stated: “I was in Delhi for the past 15 years... During the lockdown I was provided with full salary for March and very less salary for April. The salary for the month of May was unpaid. I cannot survive in Delhi on my savings without any job. So finally, I came back in the month of June to Bihar.” A few internal migrants reported that they received work under the same employer/contractor after the lockdown but complained of non-payment of wages during the lockdown period. They were forced to return to their villages due to unpaid wages, no place to live with basic facilities such as electricity and water provided by the contractor/employer and no immediate governmental protection.” (Khan and Arokkiaraj.4-5) There was a myth at the hours of pandemic that the virus is transmitted from the infected migrant workers who are coming back. In the chapter entitled “Din-Char: Gorugulo Ato Hamba Hamba Kore Kano “(Day Four: Why Do The Cows Moo) the news that he came across throughout the day, is like “why have the migrant workers returned? It is the migrant workers who return home with all the disease carried with them, they are transmitting the virus.” He asks “why will we be told that the situation is getting hard due to the return migration?”(Jaman53) Here comes the question of responsibility and attitude of the government to the migrant workers that Bulbul asks about. Though Indian constitution guarantees freedom of movement and right to take up employment anywhere in the country to all citizens under Indian Territory but there has been no integrated policy framework related to internal migrant workers. Migrant workers like Bulbul are neglected by the state and they become disillusioned with the march of time. In the chapter entitled “ Kukur Gulo Ato Dakchilo Kano?” (Why were the Dogs Barking so much?) Bulbul says by recollecting, “Our madam used to say, country is not all about boundaries. Country means people. Country means us.

But now it seems quite different. If we were the country then, why did they refuse us?”(Jaman 77) Search for home has been a recurrent trope in diaspora literature where memories of original ‘country’ or places of origin play a pivotal role. In the case of Bulbul, a domestic migrant worker, the appetite for coming back to the native place or ‘home’ has increased with time since everywhere in his India he was treated as the cultural ‘other’ by the dominant cultural groups of his workplace. In the chapter entitled “ Ami Ekhanar Noi” (I am not from here) Mutuklal, a co-worker told him in Delhi, “Certainly Delhi is the part of India. But the India of Delhi and your India are not the same. You are a Bengali, India of Bengali people is different. I am a Jharkhandi, my India is different. That is why you must be ready to hear that you are not from here.

From then on, I realised that everybody does not think that this country called India belongs to me, though I think that this is my country. That is why when I first moved to learn sewing work I was told that I am not from here, I am from Bengal. Since then I chanced to hear from everyone, be it in Chennai or Hyderabad or Pune that I am a Bengali, I am not from here.

But in the district of Burdwan when I was there for the purpose of cutting the rice crops and I heard that I am not from here but from the district of North Twenty Four Parganas, I was immediately surprised for a while and I thought that the India of Burdwan and the India of North Twenty Four Parganas are not the same thing.”(Jaman 20-21) In reality the condition

of Bulbul is that of a thousand domestic migrant workers (skilled or unskilled) that represent cultural nomadism in the ethno-religiously diverse and socio-culturally complex dynamics of modern India. This otherness resulted from the diasporic experience compels the marginalised subject, here Bulbul, to go back to his indigenous root or 'home'. Thus 'home' for Bulbul comes to signify the ethno-religious space that he is originated from, a place that he can identify himself with and his small India is a part of this big India as if a country within a country. He calls his native place by 'desh', (a country), a common term recurrently used by the most Bengali migrants to signify one's own place of nativity or 'home'. Such a 'home' reconstructed by the memories of school days, childhood, newspaper accounts, digital news becomes a mythic place of desire in his diasporic imagination. He speculates that going back home, he will marry Dolon, his lady love and open a grocery shop and spend a happy life together as it is fixed by Dolon already. In the chapter called "Din – Choy: Neem Gacher Chand" (Day six: Moon of Margosa Tree) Bulbul says, "Dolon had told, 'you have made a promise to your mother that you would not go further outside. I have kept some money for the future and you will open a grocery shop with it. You will go to the shop having a cup of tea early in the morning. I, doing all my stale work shall sit to study for the job.'" (Jaman 82) But when he arrives home all the way by cycling from Majdia (where he works as a mason), a district of Nadia to his village Sankiya under the district of North Twenty Four Parganas, he, on his arrival breaks into tears and informs his mother about his arrival. Before his mother takes him inside, a group of neighbours gathered around and burst into a wild cry by giving an alert to his mother that he must be put away in the name of the rule of social distancing as per government orders. His mother suggested for his son's home isolation but Haji chacha, the headman and political leader of the village Sankiya directly opposed the proposal in the name of rules and regulations. Bulbul tried to convince Hazi chacha by saying that he need not stay quarantined as he has no fever and no symptoms. Hazi chacha advised him to obey the elders. But in the case of Hazi uncle's son nobody imposed any such rules on him when he returns from Delhi and Bulbul's mother, pointing to the difference of treatment questions the authority and furiously challenges the relevance of obeying rules anymore. At this time Lalu and Kalo, two supporters of Hazi chacha told her not to compare between a labourer and a prince because they are of different origins. In the circle of society Hazi chacha with Lalu, Kalo, Santu and others represent a powerful authority who exert power on the peripheral characters of the village. The common people like Bulbul and others are forced to abide by the words of authority without asking them a question as they have no political powers. Thus the marginalisation of powerless people authenticates the play of power in the whole story. Interestingly enough, each single narrative of diasporic literature is in itself a vocalisation of power since the predicament of the diasporic characters results from the fact of unequal struggle between powerful and powerless people. The discourse that Hazi employs is that of persuasion and if it fails to work, he takes recourse to the discourse of threat, superiority and revenge. Hazi belongs to the dominant ruling class of the society and he is the microcosmic representation of the powers of the state (political, legislative, armed). In the chapter entitled "Amar Prothom Diner Kotha" (The Story of My First Day) Bulbul says, "everyone in our village respects him and fears him. They respect him because he is the first haji in our village and they fear him because he has made lots of money by means of politics and he has connection with people of higher level." (Jaman 24-25) Being situated in the centre of the

power he exercises great influence over the uneducated people of the village and he has a vested interest in it. Thus what he needs from them is a blind obedience and an awe-inspiring reverence. If somebody refuses to obey him he uses repressive state apparatus to dominate the working class like that of Bulbul. When Bulbul's mother refuse to obey him, one of his sycophants called Kalo threatened her with police, "Shall I call police? If they come they will arrest you all. Will that be fine?...It was true that I was afraid to hear the name of the police"(Jaman 24) The same thing happens when Bulbul was quarantined in the school for fourteen days. On one occasion as it is described in the chapter entitled "Amar Dash Namber Diner Kotha "(The Story of My Tenth Day) when Santu passes an indecent and derogatory remark about Dolon, Bulbul attacks him with shoe. Hearing the screams made by Santu and others, the police run up towards them and speak in favour of him. "Brother Santu, keep quiet. Tell me whether you want to file a complaint against him(Bulbul)."(Jaman 139) Santu, working as an agent of Haji, is invested with necessary powers to perpetrate all the criminal activities for him. In Foucauldian terms, Hazi's village, symbolic of social as well as a political institution, displays how discourse and power operate in an interrelated way. A discourse produces ' respect and terror', since it ends in domination.(Foucault,54) Power of Hazi chacha is strongly felt even in his absence and the mechanism of power terror is used by his agency by the mention and appearance of police who generate and concretise the obsessive fear in the collective psyche of common people. Foucault in his famous lecture entitled ' The order of discourse'(1970) argues "...In every society the production of discourse is at once controlled, selected, organised and redistributed by a certain member of producers whose role is to ward off its power and dangers, to gain mastery over its chance events, to evade its ponderous, formidable materiality."(Foucault,52) Under the discursive practise of difference set by the regimes of power the displaced subject like Bulbul feels marginalised, alienated and even excluded. Discourse here functions in two ways. It is an instrument and an effect of power in one hand and on the other, it is also a way of hindrance, a point for an opposing strategy.(Foucault,51) Naturally Bulbul voices his protest against the power. He protests against Santu for each of his misdeeds and unjust actions, though he faced repeated threats from him .Ultimately Bulbul has to pay the price by sacrificing his own life at their hands. He was murdered by his roommates who happened to be even his friends and fellow workers at a time. The atrocity involved in the act of killing a person is unimaginable. In the very first chapter entitled "Din-Ak: Naam Holo Amar Bulbul"(Day-One: My Name is Bulbul) he says, "My body was forcibly inserted, in a twisted way, within a plastic sack with a lungi that I used to wear at bedtime every night. With a view to give my body a round shape they broke my hands and feet with a hard wooden latch and then just like a football I was buried at the root of a palm tree. ...I could not believe even in my dream that the four roommates that I have passed my time with in a school together for thirteen days long, have killed me in this way! "(Jaman 13-14) From the first day of his arrival to the last day of his death he was treated like an outsider. He is a misfit in his own homeland. He is found to regret as his dream was shattered and his dream of an' imaginary homeland' is broken into pieces. In the chapter named "Din-Choy: Neem Gacher Chand"(Day- Six: Moon of Margosa Tree) he says, "I could not go home. The dream of staying together with Dolon remained incomplete."(Jaman 79) It is not the home that he dreamt of and his concept of 'home' is not conterminous with the 'real' one when encountered. Like Bulbul most of the migrant workers

are bound to stay like an exile in his own homeland. They are treated as impure, as virus and are kept in exile to save the so called purity of the village. It is not the fear of contamination but the disease of protest that the people in power were afraid of. If the power of resistance spreads all over from Bulbul, it would be hard for them to exist. So Bulbul is to die. 'Home' or 'point of origin' is thus nothing but an idealised phenomenon superimposed by imagination and it recedes when approached. For the migrant workers like Bulbul there is no home to stay. Home, a mythic place of desire resides only in imagination and a person who talks about the existence of home " is obliged to deal in broken mirrors, some of whose fragments have been irretrievably lost." (Rushdie 1991:11) Home is thus only to be retrieved in memory not in reality.

Note

All the translations are mine and it is done with the permission of the author Pataur Jaman.

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